

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND MOBILE COMPUTING

ISSN (Online): 2320-088X, DOI Prefix from CrossRef: 10.47760/ijcsmc, Impact Factor: 7.056

Certificate of Publication

Presented to

Okeyinka Aderemi Elisha

For publishing a paper entitled “**Towards Complexity Analysis of Some Combinatorial Algorithms Using Knapsack Model**”

in

International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing
(An Open Accessible, Fully Refereed, ISI Indexed and Peer Reviewed Monthly Journal)

VOLUME 13

ISSUE 8

August 2024

www.ijcsmc.com

Dr. Mohammad Zainuddin, Editor-In-Chief

International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Applications
ZAIN Publications, Fridhemsgatan 62, 112 46, Stockholm, Sweden